

Title: Bringing Humanity to our Data driven future – using data to solve complex social challenges

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INTRODUCTION:

Data is very powerful at telling a story, but data alone doesn't tell the full story. We need to retain our humanity as we enter a data driven future. We must use data powerfully for social good and ensure that we retain human oversight and purpose. In Australia we are hacking for social change, using data to understand and solve complex social problems and its working. TechFugees Australia and Hack4Homelessness use data to unravel complex problems and we bring data scientists together with programmers and designers to solve social problems.

AIM:

To demonstrate the powerful use of data to solve complex social problems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Case studies : TechFugees Australia a hackathon designed to support refugee settlement in Australia. Started in November 2015 the event is now across Australia and had produced unexpected solutions like Refugee Talent which is now a tech startup that places skilled refugees in jobs. The Hack4Homelessness held in September 2017 started with data – the sad reality of people falling through the cracks of ineffective social systems. We worked with the Minerva Collective who brought a team of data scientists to reveal a depth of data we can use to solve homelessness.

RESULTS:

TechFugees Australia has produced refugee led businesses solving settlement problems, like Refugee Talent – our next hackathon in Fairfield NSW where 6000 refugees have been placed allows us to use data to identify where we should hack and where the need is greatest.

Hack5Homelessness has resulted in three ideas that solve aspects of homelessness, the data showed that 60% of young people living on the streets are from foster care. The data showed a story that we couldn't know and gave people the opportunity to find new solutions to this problem.

CONCLUSIONS:

Data is key in identifying problems, complexities and areas of focus, however without humanity data is just data – a set of numbers devoid of humanity. TechFugees Australia and Hack4Homelessness prove the importance of data to establish a business case but equally important to give the data context through story telling and human stories.

KEYWORDS:

Data Hackathon Social Impact Social Change

BIOGRAPHY:

Anne-Marie advises government, business and NGOs on leveraging the innovation ecosystem to solve problems.

She preaches the gospel of disrupting the status quo and is a catalyst for change. Collaboration is her calling card and she brings together cross sector efforts to support social change initiatives.

In the past two years she cofounded TechFugees Australia and The Last Mile Australia with Annie Parker and Nicole Williamson. TechFugees is now national and runs annual hackathons and quarterly meetups to support refugee settlement. In the last 12 months Anne-Marie hosted a hack4homelessness with Disruptors Handbook and Vibewire and 80 of Sydney's brightest tech, data, design and startup experts to solve complex problems. She supported and launched Parallel Parks New Horizons initiative of enabling technology. She has spoken at numerous events

Anne-Marie reminds us theres a lot to do to help the most disadvantaged people and people outside government are key to solving these complex problems to get stuff done. She is passionate about reminding us to use our time, talent and resources to support social impact and creates the space for us to do that.

Anne-Marie is on the board of [Spark Festival](#), [VibeWire](#), [Western Sydney Women and the Autism Advisory and Support Service Board](#) and the Settlement Services International Foundation.
